

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g pot) or grams per row (g row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example 60 kg N ha; not 60 kg ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha,
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were.... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in....
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India. 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty Insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analysis are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed to pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common not trade names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity etc.)

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Varietal groups of rice cultivars in West Africa and the Americas

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Rice groups classified by genotypic analysis for esterase isoenzymes corresponded well to the conventional varietal groups and geographic distributions of land races. Genotype 1 dominated in India and Sri Lanka, and corresponded

to indica (aman, aus, and boro paddy in West Bengal); genotype 3, common in South China and Vietnam, corresponded to sinica (Chinese hsen rices); and genotype 6 in northern areas such as North China and Japan corresponded to japonica (Chinese keng type). Genotypes 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12, scattered in hilly areas of Southeast Asia, corresponded to javanicas.

The cultivars in the Americas and Africa showed unusual enzyme geno-

Esterase genotype distribution in West Africa and the Americas.

types. In West Africa, half were genotypes 1 and 3. The others, which may be major traditional cultivars, comprised genotypes 7, 12, 11, 8. The latter group may belong to a member of hill rices in Southeast Asia (see figure).

North America, particularly Texas State, showed variations of isoenzyme genotypes between japonica and javan-

ica. Consequently their origin may not be India and South China.

South America, particularly Brazil, showed simple variation. Most cultivars belong to genotypes 12 and 11, corresponding to the typical javanicas. A similar variation is found only on Sumatra island in Asia. West Africa and the Americas have a particular type of este-

rase isoenzyme genotypes. These are not indica (Indian rices) or sinica (Chinese hsien), but are more closely related hill rices or javanicas found in Upper Burma, northern Thailand, Laos, Sumatra, and southern Yunnan Province of China. ✎

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Performance of IR42 and IR48 in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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IRRI early and intermediate maturity varieties and breeding lines have revolutionized rice cultivation in Vietnam. Two rice crops each year are now grown where one low-yielding, late-maturing local variety once grew. More than a dozen IRRI lines have been named and released for large-scale cultivation.

More than 65% of the rice area in Cuu Long Delta (Vietnamese portion of Mekong Delta) is planted to IRRI varie-

ties. Some popular varieties in large-scale cultivation are: NN3A (IR36), NN6A (IR2307-247-2-2-3), NN7A (IR9129-192-2-3-5), NN8A (IR2070-199-3-6-6), and NN2B (IR2823-399-5-6). Average yields are 3.5-4.0 t/ha.

NN4B (IR42) and NN5B (IR48) were introduced in 1981. Their performance, particularly in adverse soils, is encouraging (Table 1). Both varieties have intermediate maturity (130-145 days), tolerance for soil stresses, semitall plant height (100-120 cm), and resist lodging. NN4B yields higher on saline soils than the popular local variety Than Nong Do. NN5B yields more than local varieties Tieu Mo and Bay Danh on acid sulfate soils. Both varieties have yielded

more than an earlier IRRI line, NN2B, on alluvial soils. In seed multiplication plots at 10 sites, yields were 4-9 t/ha.

Both varieties resist brown planthopper, and NN5B resists rice blast (Table 2). Neither variety, however, resists sheath blight. Both varieties are popular with farmers because they are generally free of pest damage in normal field conditions.

Because NN4B and NN5B are popular, produce high yields, and are insect and disease resistant the Cuu Long RRI is making special efforts to rapidly multiply seeds on a large scale. ✎

Table 1. Yield level^a of NN4B and NN5B in early mua season (May-Oct), Cuu Long, Delta, Vietnam.

Variety	Hau Giang Province (alluvial soil)			Long An Province (acid sulfate soil), rainfed wetland		Minh Hai Province (saline soil), rainfed lowland,	Average yield (t/ha)
	Irrigated, 1980	Rainfed 1979 1981		1980	1981	1980	
NN4B (IR42)	6.63 a	3.38 a	3.13 b	2.91 b	3.00 b	3.96 a	3.84
NN5B (IR48)	6.45 a	3.45 a	4.18 a	3.53 a	4.20 a	3.54 b	4.22
Check ^b	4.20 b	2.85 b	3.13 b	2.60 b	2.90 b	3.15 c	3.18

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5%. ^bVariety check: alluvial: NN2B; acid sulfate: Tieu Mo (1980), Bay Danh (1981); saline: Than Nong Do.

Table 2. Reaction of NN4B and NN5B to rice pest in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam.^a

Variety	Brown planthopper		Leaf blast		Bacterial leaf blight		Sheath blight	
	Infested (%)	Reaction	Scale (0-9)	Reaction	Scale (0-9)	Reaction	Disease index (%)	Reaction
NN4B (IR42)	14	R	4-7	MS-S	3	MR	90	HS
NN5B (IR48)	30	MR	1	R	5	MS	80	S
Resistant check ^b	26	MR	1	R	1	R	100	HS
Susceptible check ^b	100	HS	4-9	MS-HS	8	S	100	HS

^aArtificial infestation, using IRRI test and scoring procedures. R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^bResistant check for BPH: IR36, LB: Tetep, BLB: Cempo Selak, ShB: IET4699. Susceptible check for BPH: TN1, LB: NN7a BLB: IR8, ShB: IR36.